

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A Note on Separation Axioms in Kasaj Topological Spaces

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Abstract

Objectives: The separation axioms are about the use of kasaj topological means to distinguish disjoint sets and distinct points and the purpose of this work is to investigate the spaces namely $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]$ - T_0 spaces, $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]$ - T_1 spaces, $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]$ - T_2 spaces by utilizing $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]$ -open sets in Kasaj topological spaces. Also, we discuss their relationship with existing concepts in Kasaj topological spaces. **Methods:** Any two Kasaj topologically distinguishable points must be distinct, and any two separated points must be Kasaj topologically distinguishable. **Finding:** This study consists of three separation axioms namely $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]$ - T_0 spaces, $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]$ - T_1 spaces, $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]$ - T_2 spaces by utilizing $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]$ -open sets in Kasaj topological spaces. **Novelty:** This study uses their relationship with existing concepts in Kasaj topological spaces.

AMS Classification: 54A05,54B05,54A99.

Keywords: KS_{gp} - T_0 spaces; KS_{gsp} - T_0 space; KS_{gp} - T_1 spaces; KS_{gsp} - T_1 spaces; KS_{gp} - T_2 spaces; KS_{gsp} - T_2 spaces

1 Introduction

In 2021, Abdelwaheb Mhemdi, Tareq M. Al-shami⁽¹⁾ introduced the concept of functionally separation axioms on general topology. In 2021 Das & Pramanik⁽²⁾ introduced the concept of ultra neutrosophic set. In 2022, Das and Tripathy⁽³⁾ introduced the concept of separation axioms on spatial topological spaces. In 2022, Das and Tripathy,⁽⁴⁾ introduced the concept of rough pentapartitioned neutrosophic set. In 2022, Das & Tripathy⁽⁵⁾ introduced the concept of neutrosophic pre-I-open set. In 2022, Das & Tripathy⁽⁶⁾ introduced the concept of neutrosophic set and systems. In 2020, Kashyap G. Rachchh and Sajeed⁽⁷⁾ introduced the concept of kasaj topological spaces. Further, the same year auothers⁽⁸⁾ introduced the concept of Kasaj generalized closed sets in Kasaj topological spaces. In 2022, Sathishmohan⁽⁹⁾ et.al introduced the new type of closed sets known as $KS_{gp}(KS_{gsp})$ -closed sets in Kasaj topological spaces and obtained many interesting results. In 2023, Li, PY., Liu, WL., Mou,⁽¹⁰⁾ et al. introduced

the concept of separation axioms of topological rough groups. In this paper, we shall define $KS-T_0$ spaces, $KS-T_1$ spaces, $KS-T_2$ spaces, KS pre- T_0 spaces, KS pre- T_1 spaces, KS pre- T_2 spaces, $KS_\alpha-T_0$ spaces, $KS_\alpha-T_1$ spaces, $KS_\alpha-T_2$ spaces, $KS_\beta-T_0$ spaces, $KS_\beta-T_1$ spaces, $KS_\beta-T_2$ spaces, KS_g [KS_{gp}, KS_{gsp}]- T_0 spaces, KS_g [KS_{gp}, KS_{gsp}]- T_1 spaces, KS_g [KS_{gp}, KS_{gsp}]- T_2 spaces in Kasaj topological spaces.

2 Methodology

In this study, the following methodologies are used.

In $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]-T_0$ spaces, $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]-T_1$ spaces, if we take each pair of distinct points and then there exists $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]$ -open sets such that the distinct points are belongs to any one of the $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]$ -open sets in $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]-T_0$ spaces, $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]-T_1$ spaces. But in $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]-T_2$ spaces, if we take each pair of distinct points and then there exists $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]$ -open sets such that the distinct points are belongs to any one of the $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]$ -open sets and so intersection of two $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]$ -open sets are empty.

3 Result and discussion

3.1 Properties of $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]-T_0$ Spaces

The objective of this section is to introduce and investigate the concepts of $KS_{gp} [KS_{gsp}]-T_0$ Spaces in Kasaj Topological Spaces.

Definition 3.1 .1. A Kasaj Topological Spaces U is called

(i) $KS-T_0$ iff to each pair of distinct points $x, y \in U$, there exists a KS -open set G such that either $x \in G$ and $y \notin G$ or $x \notin G$ and $y \in G$.

(ii) KS -pre- T_0 iff to each pair of distinct points $x, y \in U$, there exists a KS -pre-open set G such that either $x \in G$ and $y \notin G$ or $x \notin G$ and $y \in G$.

(iii) $KS_\beta-T_0$ iff to each pair of distinct points $x, y \in U$, there exists a KS_β -open set G such that either $x \in G$ and $y \notin G$ or $x \notin G$ and $y \in G$.

(iv) $KS_{gp}-T_0$ iff to each pair of distinct points $x, y \in U$, there exists a KS_{gp} -open set G such that either $x \in G$ and $y \notin G$ or $x \notin G$ and $y \in G$.

(v) $KS_{gsp}-T_0$ iff to each pair of distinct points $x, y \in U$, there exists a KS_{gsp} -open set G such that either $x \in G$ and $y \notin G$ or $x \notin G$ and $y \in G$.

Theorem 3.1.2. In a Kasaj Topological Spaces $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$. Then

(i) Every $KS-T_0$ space is $(KS$ pre- $T_0, KS_\alpha-T_0, KS_\beta-T_0, KS_g-T_0) KS_{gp}-T_0$.

(ii) Every KS pre- T_0 space is $(KS_\beta-T_0) KS_{gp}-T_0$.

(iii) Every $KS_\alpha-T_0$ space is $(KS$ pre- $T_0, KS_\beta-T_0) KS_{gp}-T_0$

(iv) Every $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space is $KS_{gp}-T_0$.

Proof:

(i) Suppose U is $KS-T_0$ space. Let x and y be two distinct points in U . Since U is $KS-T_0$, there exists an KS -open set G containing either $x \in G$ and $y \notin G$ or $x \notin G$ and $y \in G$. Since every KS -open set is $(KS$ pre-open, KS_α - open, KS_β - open, KS_g - open) KS_{gp} -open, G is $(KS$ pre-open, KS_α - open, KS_β - open, KS_g - open) KS_{gp} -open. Hence, U is $(KS$ pre- $T_0, KS_\alpha-T_0, KS_\beta-T_0, KS_g-T_0) KS_{gp}-T_0$.

Proof of (ii), (iii), (iv) are similar to (i).

Converse of the above the theorem need not be true as shown in the following example.

Example 3.1.3. Let $U = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$, with $U \setminus R = \{b, d\}, \{c, e\}, \{a\}$ and $X = \{a, b\}$. Then the nano topology, $\tau_R(X) = \{U, \emptyset, \{a\}, \{b, d\}, \{b, d\}\}$. $S = \{b\}$, $S' = \{a, c, d, e\}$. Then $x = \{b\}$, $y = \{e\}$ it is $KS_{gp}-T_0-T_0$ but not in $KS-T_0, KS$ pre- $T_0, KS_\beta-T_0, KS_g-T_0$.

Theorem 3.1.4. If U is a $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space and V is a subspace of U , then V is also $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space.

Proof:

Let U be a $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space and V be a subspace of U . To show that V is $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space. Let $x, y \in V$ with $x \neq y$. Since $V \subseteq U$, we have $x, y \in U$. But U is $KS_{gp}-T_0$, so there exists an KS_{gp} -open set G such that G contains only one of them, say, $x \in G$ and $y \notin G$. Then $V \cap G$ is KS_{gp} -open set in V such that $x \in V \cap G$ and $y \notin V \cap G$. Hence V is $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space.

Theorem 3.1.5. A Kasaj Topological Spaces U is $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space iff the KS_{gp} -closures of distinct points are distinct.

Proof:

Assume that U is a $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space. Let $x, y \in U$ with $x \neq y$. Since U is $KS_{gp}-T_0$, there is an KS_{gp} -open set G such that G contains only one of them, say, $x \in G$ and $y \notin G$. Since G is an KS_{gp} -open set containing x and $G \cap (y) = \emptyset$, we have $x \notin KS_{gp}cl(\{y\})$. But $x \in KS_{gp}cl(\{x\})$. So $KS_{gp}cl(\{x\}) \neq KS_{gp}cl(\{y\})$.

Conversely, assume that for $x \neq y$, $KS_{gpc}(\{x\}) \neq KS_{gpc}(\{y\})$. So there exists $z \notin KS_{gpc}(\{x\})$ such that $z \in KS_{gpc}(\{y\})$. Now if $x \in KS_{gpc}(\{y\})$, then $\{x\} \subseteq KS_{gpc}(\{y\})$ this implies that $KS_{gpc}(\{x\}) \subseteq KS_{gpc}(\{y\})$ which implied $z \in KS_{gpc}(\{x\})$. Since $z \in KS_{gpc}(\{x\})$. This is a contradiction. So $x \in KS_{gpc}(\{y\}) = F$, this implies $x \in F^c$, since $y \in F$, $y \notin F^c$. Thus, F^c is an KS_{gp} -open set containing x but not y . Hence, U is $KS_{gp}-T_0$.

Theorem 3.1.6. In a Kasaj Topological Spaces $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$. Then

- (i) Every $KS-T_0$ space is $KS_{gp}-T_0$.
- (ii) Every KS pre- T_0 space is $KS_{gp}-T_0$.
- (iii) Every $KS_\alpha - T_0$ space is $KS_{gp} - T_0$.
- (iv) Every $KS_\beta - T_0$ space is $KS_{gp}-T_0$.
- (v) Every $KS_g - T_0$ space is $KS_{gp}-T_0$.
- (vi) Every $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space is $KS_{gp}-T_0$.

Proof:

It is obvious from theorem 3.1.2.

Converse of the above the theorem need not be true as shown in the following example.

Example 3.1.7. Let $U = \{a,b,c,d,e\}$, with $U \setminus R = \{a,e\}, \{c, d\}, \{b\}$ and $X = \{b,c\}$. Then the nano topology, $\tau_R(X) = \{U, \emptyset, \{b\}, \{b,c,d\}, \{c,d\}\}$. $S = \{c\}$, $S' = \{a, b, d, e\}$. Then $x = \{a\}$, $y = \{c\}$ it is $KS_{gp}-T_0$ but not in $KS-T_0, KS$ pre- $T_0, KS_\alpha-T_0, KS_\beta-T_0, KS_g-T_0, KS_{gp}-T_0$.

Theorem 3.1.8. If U is a $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space and V is a subspace of U , then V is also $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space.

Proof:

Let U be a $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space and V be a subspace of U . To show that V is $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space. Let $x,y \in V$ with $x \neq y$. Since $V \subseteq U$, we have $x,y \in U$. But U is $KS_{gp}-T_0$, so there exists an KS_{gp} -open set G such that G contains only one of them, say, $x \in G$ and $y \notin G$. Then $V \cap G$ is KS_{gp} -open set in V such that $x \in V \cap G$ and $y \notin V \cap G$. Hence V is $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space.

Theorem 3.1.9. A Kasaj Topological Spaces U is $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space iff the KS_{gp} -closures of distinct points are distinct.

Proof:

Assume that U is a $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space. Let $x,y \in U$ with $x \neq y$. Since U is $KS_{gp}-T_0$, there is an KS_{gp} -open set G such that G contains only one of them, say, $x \in G$ and $y \notin G$. Since G is an KS_{gp} -open set containing x and $G \cap (y) = \emptyset$, we have $x \notin KS_{gpc}(\{y\})$. But $x \in KS_{gpc}(\{x\})$. So $KS_{gpc}(\{x\}) \neq KS_{gpc}(\{y\})$.

Conversely, assume that for $x \neq y$, $KS_{gpc}(\{x\}) \neq KS_{gpc}(\{y\})$. So there exists $z \notin KS_{gpc}(\{x\})$ such that $z \in KS_{gpc}(\{y\})$. Now if $x \in KS_{gpc}(\{y\})$, then $\{x\} \subseteq KS_{gpc}(\{y\})$ this implies that $KS_{gpc}(\{x\}) \subseteq KS_{gpc}(\{y\})$ which implied $z \in KS_{gpc}(\{x\})$. Since $z \in KS_{gpc}(\{x\})$. This is a contradiction. So $x \in KS_{gpc}(\{y\}) = F$, this implies $x \in F^c$, since $y \in F$, $y \notin F^c$. Thus, F^c is an KS_{gp} -open set containing x but not y . Hence U is $KS_{gp}-T_0$.

3.2 Properties of $KS_{gp} [KS_{gp}]-T_1$ Spaces

Developing and analyzing the concepts of $KS_{gp} [KS_{gp}]-T_1$ Spaces in Kasaj Topological Spaces is the purpose of this study.

Definition 3.2.1. A Kasaj Topological Spaces U is called

- (i) $KS-T_1$ space if whenever x and y are distinct points in U , there is an KS -open set F and G such that $x \in F$ and $y \notin F$, and $y \in G$ and $x \notin G$.
- (ii) KS pre- T_1 space if whenever x and y are distinct points in U , there is an KS -pre-open set F and G such that $x \in F$ and $y \notin F$, and $y \in G$ and $x \notin G$.
- (iii) $KS_\beta - T_1$ space if whenever x and y are distinct points in U , there is an KS_β -open set F and G such that $x \in F$ and $y \notin F$, and $y \in G$ and $x \notin G$.
- (iv) $KS_g - T_1$ space if whenever x and y are distinct points in U , there is an KS_g -open set F and G such that $x \in F$ and $y \notin F$, and $y \in G$ and $x \notin G$.
- (v) $KS_{gp}-T_1$ space if whenever x and y are distinct points in U , there is an KS_{gp} -open set F and G such that $x \in F$ and $y \notin F$, and $y \in G$ and $x \notin G$.

Theorem 3.2.2. In a Kasaj Topological Spaces $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$. Then

- (i) Every $KS-T_1$ space is $(KS$ pre- $T_1, KS_\alpha-T_1, KS_\beta-T_1, KS_g-T_1) KS_{gp}-T_1$.
- (ii) Every KS pre- T_1 space is $(KS_\beta - T_1) KS_{gp}-T_1$.
- (iii) Every $KS_\alpha - T_1$ space is $(KS$ pre- $T_1, KS_\beta - T_1) KS_{gp} - T_1$.
- (iv) Every $KS_g - T_1$ space is $KS_{gp} - T_1$.

Proof:

(i) Suppose U is $KS-T_1$ space. Let x and y be two distinct points in U . Since U is $KS-T_1$, there exists an KS -open sets F and G such that $x \in F$ and $y \notin F$, and $y \in G$ and $x \notin G$. Since every KS -open set is $(KS$ -pre-open, KS_α -open, KS_β -open, KS_g -open)

KS_{gp} -open, F and G are KS -open set is (KS -pre-open, KS_{α} -open, KS_{β} -open, KS_g -open) KS_{gp} -open. Hence, U is KS_{gp} - T_1 .

Proof of (ii), (iii), (iv) are similar to (i).

Converse of the above the theorem need not be true as shown in the following example.

Example 3.2.3. Let $U = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$, with $U \setminus R = \{\{d, e\}, \{a, b\}, \{c\}\}$ and $X = \{a, c\}$. Then the nano topology, $\tau_R(X) = \{U, \emptyset, \{c\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b\}\}$. $S = \{a\}$, $S' = \{b, c, d, e\}$. Then $x = \{a\}$, $y = \{b\}$ it is KS_{gp} - T_1 but not in KS - T_1 , KS pre- T_1 , KS_{α} - T_1 , KS_g - T_1 .

Theorem 3.2.4. Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a Kasaj Topological Space, then for each KS_{gp} - T_1 space is KS_{gp} - T_0 space.

Proof:

Let U be a KS_{gp} - T_1 space and let x and y be two distinct points of U , there exists KS_{gp} -open sets G and H such that $x \in G$, $y \notin G$ and $x \notin H$, $y \in H$. We have $x \in G$, $y \notin G$. Therefore, U is KS_{gp} - T_0 space.

Theorem 3.2.5. If U is a KS_{gp} - T_1 space and V is a subspace of U , then V is also KS_{gp} - T_1 space.

Proof:

Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a KS_{gp} - T_1 space and $(V, \tau_R(Y), KS_R(Y))$ be a subspace U . Let $x, y \in V$ with $x \neq y$. Since $V \subseteq U$, we have $x, y \in U$. Since U is KS_{gp} - T_1 , then there exists KS_{gp} -open sets G and H such that $x \in G$, $y \notin G$ and $y \in H$, $x \notin H$. Let $M = V \cap G$ and $N = V \cap H$. Then M and N are KS_{gp} -open sets in V . Also $x \in M$, $y \notin M$ and $y \in N$, $x \notin N$. Hence, $(V, \tau_R(Y), KS_R(Y))$ is also a KS_{gp} - T_1 space.

Theorem 3.2.6. A Kasaj Topological Space $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ is KS_{gp} - T_1 iff the each one-point set is KS_{gp} -closed.

Proof:

Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a KS_{gp} - T_1 space. Let $x \in U$, Then for each $y \in U - \{x\}$ there exists a KS_{gp} -open set F such that $y \in F$ and $x \notin F$, the sets $\{x\}$ and F are disjoint. That is $\{x\} \cap F = \emptyset$ this implies that $F \subseteq U - \{x\}$. Thus, $y \in F \subseteq U - \{x\}$ this implies that $U - \{x\}$ is an KS_{gp} -open set this implies that $\{x\}$ is KS_{gp} -closed in U .

Conversely, suppose $\{x\}$ is KS_{gp} -closed. Let $x, y \in U$ with $x \neq y$. So $U - \{x\}$ is an KS_{gp} -open set containing y but not x . Also, $U - \{y\}$ is an KS_{gp} -open set containing x but not y . Hence, U is a KS_{gp} - T_1 space.

Theorem 3.2.7. A Kasaj Topological Space $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ is KS_{gp} - T_1 iff every finite subset of U is KS_{gp} -closed set in U .

Proof:

Assume that U is KS_{gp} - T_1 . Let G be a finite subset of U . Let $G = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$. Then $G = \{x_1\} \cup \{x_2\} \cup \dots \cup \{x_n\}$ is KS_{gp} -closed, being a finite union of KS_{gp} -closed sets. Conversely, let each finite subset of U is KS_{gp} -closed in U . Then $\{x\}$ is KS_{gp} -closed, since it is finite. Since each singleton is KS_{gp} -closed, U is KS_{gp} - T_1 .

Theorem 3.2.8. A Kasaj Topological Space $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ is KS_{gp} - T_1 iff the intersection of all KS_{gp} -neighbourhoods of any point x in U is the singleton $\{x\}$.

Proof:

Assume that U is KS_{gp} - T_1 . Let $x \in U$. Let G be the intersection of all KS_{gp} -neighbourhoods of x . Let y be any point in U different from x . Since U is KS_{gp} - T_1 , there exists a KS_{gp} -neighbourhood M of x such that $y \notin M$. Since $y \notin M$, we have $y \notin G$. Since G is the intersection of all KS_{gp} -neighbourhoods of x . Since $y \notin G$, no point different from x in G . Hence $G = \{x\}$.

Conversely, assume that intersection of all KS_{gp} -neighbourhoods of x in U is $\{x\}$. To prove that U is KS_{gp} - T_1 , let $x, y \in U$ with $x \neq y$.

Let $G = \cap \{\text{all } KS_{gp}\text{-neighbourhoods of } x \text{ in } U\}$. Then $G = \{x\}$.

Let $H = \cap \{\text{all } KS_{gp}\text{-neighbourhoods of } y \text{ in } U\}$. Then $H = \{y\}$.

Since $y \notin x$, we have $y \notin G$ then there exists KS_{gp} -neighbourhoods J of x with $y \notin J$. Since $x \neq y$, $x \notin K$ this implies that KS_{gp} -neighbourhoods $y \in K$ with $x \notin K$. Hence U is KS_{gp} - T_1 .

Theorem 3.2.9. In a Kasaj Topological Spaces $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$. Then

(i) Every KS - T_1 space is KS_{gp} - T_1 .

(ii) Every KS pre- T_1 space is KS_{gp} - T_1 .

(iii) Every KS_{α} - T_1 space is KS_{gp} - T_1 .

(iv) Every KS_{β} - T_1 space is KS_{gp} - T_1 .

(v) Every KS_g - T_1 space is KS_{gp} - T_1 .

Proof:

It is obvious from theorem 3.2.2.

Converse of the above the theorem need not be true as shown in the following example.

Example 3.2.10. Let $U = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$, with $U \setminus R = \{\{a, d\}, \{b, e\}, \{c\}\}$ and $X = \{a, c\}$. Then the nano topology, $\tau_R(X) = \{U, \emptyset, \{c\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, d\}\}$. $S = \{a\}$, $S' = \{b, c, d, e\}$. Then $x = \{a\}$, $y = \{b\}$ it is KS_{gp} - T_1 but not in KS - T_1 , KS pre T_1 , KS_{α} - T_1 , KS_{β} - T_1 , KS_g - T_1 .

Theorem 3.2.11. Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a Kasaj Topological Space, then for each KS_{gp} - T_1 space is KS_{gp} - T_0 space.

Proof:

Let U be a $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_1$ space and let x and y be two distinct points of U , there exists KS_{gsp} -open sets G and H such that $x \in G$, $y \notin G$ and $x \notin H$, $y \in H$. We have $x \in G$, $y \notin G$. Therefore, U is $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_0$ space.

Theorem 3.2.12. If U is a $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_1$ space and V is a subspace of U , then V is also $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_1$ space.

Proof:

Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_1$ space and $(V, \tau_R(Y), KS_R(Y))$ be a subspace U . Let $x, y \in V$ with $x \neq y$. Since $V \subseteq U$, we have $x, y \in U$. Since U is $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_1$, then there exists KS_{gsp} -open sets G and H such that $x \in G$, $y \notin G$ and $y \in H$, $x \notin H$. Let $M = V \cap G$ and $N = V \cap H$. Then M and N are KS_{gsp} -open sets in V . Also $x \in M$, $y \notin M$ and $y \in N$, $x \notin N$. Hence $(V, \tau_R(Y), KS_R(Y))$ is also a $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_1$ space.

Theorem 3.2.13. A Kasaj Topological Space $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ is $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_1$ iff the each one-point set is KS_{gsp} -closed.

Proof:

Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_1$ space. Let $x \in U$, Then for each $y \in U - \{x\}$ there exists a KS_{gsp} -open set F such that $y \in F$ and $x \notin F$, the sets $\{x\}$ and F are disjoint. That is $\{x\} \cap F = \emptyset$ this implies that $F \subseteq U - \{x\}$. Thus, $y \in F \subseteq U - \{x\}$ this implies that $U - \{x\}$ is an KS_{gsp} -open set this implies that $\{x\}$ is KS_{gsp} -closed in U . Conversely, suppose $\{x\}$ is KS_{gsp} -closed. Let $x, y \in U$ with $x \neq y$. So $U - \{x\}$ is an KS_{gsp} -open set containing y but not x . Also $U - \{y\}$ is an KS_{gsp} -open set containing x but not y . Hence U is a $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_1$ space.

Theorem 3.2.14. A Kasaj Topological Space $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ is $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_1$ iff every finite subset of U is KS_{gsp} -closed set in U .

Proof:

Assume that U is $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_1$. Let G be a finite subset of U . Let $G = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$. Then $G = \{x_1\} \cup \{x_2\} \dots \cup \{x_n\}$ is KS_{gsp} -closed, being a finite union of KS_{gsp} -closed sets.

Conversely, let each finite subset of U is KS_{gsp} -closed in U . Then $\{x\}$ is KS_{gsp} -closed, since it is finite. Since each singleton is KS_{gsp} -closed, U is $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_1$.

Theorem 3.2.15. A Kasaj Topological Space $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ is $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_1$ iff the intersection of all KS_{gsp} -neighbourhoods of any point x in U is the singleton $\{x\}$.

Proof:

Assume that U is $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_1$. Let $x \in U$. Let G be the intersection of all KS_{gsp} -neighbourhoods of x . Let y be any point in U different from x . Since U is $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_1$, there exists a KS_{gsp} -neighbourhood M of x such that $y \notin M$. Since $y \notin M$, we have $y \notin G$. Since G is the intersection of all KS_{gsp} -neighbourhoods of x . Since $y \notin G$, no point different from x in G . Hence $G = \{x\}$.

Conversely, assume that intersection of all KS_{gsp} -neighbourhoods of x in U is $\{x\}$. To prove that U is $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_1$, let $x, y \in U$ with $x \neq y$.

Let $G = \cap \{\text{all } KS_{gsp}\text{-neighbourhoods of } x \text{ in } U\}$. Then $G = \{x\}$.

Let $H = \cap \{\text{all } KS_{gsp}\text{-neighbourhoods of } y \text{ in } U\}$. Then $H = \{y\}$.

Since $y \neq x$, we have $y \notin G$ then there exists KS_{gsp} -neighbourhoods J of x with $y \notin J$. Since $x \neq y$, $x \notin K$ this implies that KS_{gsp} -neighbourhoods $y \in K$ with $x \notin K$. Hence, U is $KS_{gsp}\text{-}T_1$.

3.3 Properties of $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]\text{-}T_2$ Spaces

Describing and researching the notations of $KS_{gp}[KS_{gsp}]\text{-}T_2$ Spaces in Kasaj Topological Spaces is the motto of this section.

Definition 3.3.1. A Kasaj topological spaces U is called

(i) $KS\text{-}T_2$ space if for each pair of distinct points x, y in U , there exists an KS -open set F and G such that $x \in F$, $y \in G$ and $F \cap G = \emptyset$.

(ii) $KS\text{ pre-}T_2$ space if for each pair of distinct points x, y in U , there exists an KS pre-open set F and G such that $x \in F$, $y \in G$ and $F \cap G = \emptyset$.

(iii) $KS_\beta\text{-}T_2$ space if for each pair of distinct points x, y in U , there exists an KS_β -open set F and G such that $x \in F$, $y \in G$ and $F \cap G = \emptyset$.

(iv) $KS_{gp}\text{-}T_2$ space if for each pair of distinct points x, y in U , there exists an KS_{gp} -open set F and G such that $x \in F$, $y \in G$ and $F \cap G = \emptyset$.

(v) $KS_{\beta gsp}\text{-}T_2$ space if for each pair of distinct points x, y in U , there exists an $KS_{\beta gsp}$ -open set F and G such that $x \in F$, $y \in G$ and $F \cap G = \emptyset$.

Theorem 3.3.2. In a Kasaj Topological Spaces $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$. Then

(i) Every $KS\text{-}T_2$ space is $(KS\text{ pre-}T_2, KS_\alpha\text{-}T_2, KS_\beta\text{-}T_2, KS_g\text{-}T_2) KS_{gp}\text{-}T_2$.

(ii) Every $KS\text{ pre-}T_2$ space is $(KS_\beta\text{-}T_2) KS_{gp}\text{-}T_2$.

(iii) Every $KS_\alpha\text{-}T_2$ space is $(KS\text{ pre-}T_2, KS_\beta\text{-}T_2) KS_{gp}\text{-}T_2$.

(iv) Every KS_g-T_2 space is $KS_{gp}-T_2$.

Proof:

(i) Suppose U is $KS-T_2$ space. Let x and y be two distinct points in U . Since U is $KS-T_2$, there exists an KS -open sets F and G such that $x \in F$ and $y \in G$. Since every KS -open set is (KS -pre-open, KS_α -open, KS_β -open, KS_g -open) KS_{gp} -open, F and G are distinct (KS -pre open, KS_α -open, KS_β -open, KS_g -open) KS_{gp} -open sets such that $x \in F$ and $y \in G$. Hence U is $KS_{gp}-T_2$.

Proof of (ii), (iii), (iv) are similar to (i).

Converse of the above the theorem need not be true as shown in the following example.

Example 3.3.3. Let $U = \{a,b,c,d,e\}$, with $U \setminus R = \{b,d\}, \{c,e\}, \{a\}$ and $X = \{a, c\}$. Then the nanotopology, $\tau_R(X) = \{U, \emptyset, \{a, c, e\}, \{c, e\}\}$. $S = \{b\}$, $S' = \{a, b, d, e\}$. Then $x = \{a\}$, $y = \{b\}$ it is $KS_{gp}-T_2$ but not in $KS-T_2$, KS pre- T_2 , $KS_\alpha-T_2$, KS_g-T_2 .

Theorem 3.3.4. Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a Kasaj Topological Space, then for each $KS_{gp}-T_2$ space is $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space.

Proof:

Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a $KS_{gp}-T_2$ space and let $x, y \in U$, $x \neq y$, then there exists a two distinct KS_{gp} -open sets $G, H \subseteq U$ such that $x \in G$, $y \in H$, $G \cap H = \emptyset$. Since $G \cap H = \emptyset$, $x \in G$, $y \notin G$ and $x \notin H$, $y \in H$. Hence U is $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space.

Theorem 3.3.5. Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a Kasaj Topological Space, then for each $KS_{gp}-T_2$ space is $KS_{gp}-T_1$ space.

Proof:

Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a $KS_{gp}-T_2$ space and let $x, y \in U$, $x \neq y$, then there exists a two distinct KS_{gp} -open sets G, H such that $x \in G$, $y \notin G$ and $y \in H$, $x \notin H$, $G \cap H = \emptyset$. Therefore, U is $KS_{gp}-T_1$ space.

Theorem 3.3.6. If U is a $KS_{gp}-T_2$ space and V is a subspace of U , then V is also $KS_{gp}-T_2$ space.

Proof:

Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a $KS_{gp}-T_2$ space and $(V, \tau_R(Y), KS_R(Y))$ be a subspace of U . Let $x, y \in V$ with $x \neq y$. Then $x, y \in U$. Since U is $KS_{gp}-T_2$, there exists KS_{gp} -open sets F and G such that $x \in F$, $y \in G$ and $F \cap G = \emptyset$. Thus, we have $F \cap V, G \cap V$ are KS_{gp} -open set in V , $(F \cap V) \cap (G \cap V) = \emptyset$, $x \in F \cap V$, $y \in G \cap V$. Hence $(V, \tau_R(Y), KS_R(Y))$ is $KS_{gp}-T_2$ space.

Theorem 3.3.7. In a Kasaj Topological Spaces $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$. Then

(i) Every $KS-T_2$ space is $KS_{gp}-T_2$.

(ii) Every KS pre- T_2 space is $KS_{gp}-T_2$.

(iii) Every $KS_\alpha-T_2$ space is $KS_{gp}-T_2$.

(iv) Every $KS_\beta-T_2$ space is $KS_{gp}-T_2$.

(v) Every KS_g-T_2 space is $KS_{gp}-T_2$.

Proof:

It is obvious from theorem 3.3.2.

Converse of the above the theorem need not be true as shown in the following example.

Example 3.3.8. Let $U = \{a,b, c, d, e\}$, with $U \setminus R = \{\{a,b\}, \{c,d\}, \{e\}\}$ and $X = \{a,e\}$. Then the nano topology, $\tau_R(X) = \{U, \emptyset, \{e\}, \{a, b, e\}, \{a,b\}\}$. $S = \{a\}$, $S' = \{b, c, d, e\}$. Then $x = \{c\}$, $y = \{d\}$ it is $KS_{gp}-T_2$ but not in $KS-T_2$, KS pre- T_2 , $KS_\alpha-T_2$, $KS_\beta-T_2$, KS_g-T_2 .

Theorem 3.3.9. Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a Kasaj Topological Space, then for each $KS_{gp}-T_2$ space is $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space.

Proof:

Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a $KS_{gp}-T_2$ space and let $x, y \in U$, $x \neq y$, then there exists a two distinct KS_{gp} -open sets $G, H \subseteq U$ such that $x \in G$, $y \in H$, $G \cap H = \emptyset$. Since $G \cap H = \emptyset$, $x \in G$, $y \notin G$ and $x \notin H$, $y \in H$. Hence, U is $KS_{gp}-T_0$ space.

Theorem 3.3.10. Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a Kasaj Topological Space, then for each $KS_{gp}-T_2$ space is $KS_{gp}-T_1$ space.

Proof:

Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a $KS_{gp}-T_2$ space and let $x, y \in U$, $x \neq y$, then there exists a two distinct KS_{gp} -open sets G, H such that $x \in G$, $y \notin G$ and $y \in H$, $x \notin H$, $G \cap H = \emptyset$. Therefore, U is $KS_{gp}-T_1$ space.

Theorem 3.3.11. If U is a $KS_{gp}-T_2$ space and V is a subspace of U , then V is also $KS_{gp}-T_2$ space.

Proof:

Let $(U, \tau_R(X), KS_R(X))$ be a $KS_{gp}-T_2$ space and $(V, \tau_R(Y), KS_R(Y))$ be a subspace of U . Let $x, y \in V$ with $x \neq y$. Then $x, y \in U$. Since U is $KS_{gp}-T_2$, there exists KS_{gp} -open sets F and G such that $x \in F$, $y \in G$ and $F \cap G = \emptyset$. Thus, we have $F \cap V, G \cap V$ are KS_{gp} -open set in V , $(F \cap V) \cap (G \cap V) = \emptyset$, $x \in F \cap V$, $y \in G \cap V$. Hence $(V, \tau_R(Y), KS_R(Y))$ is $KS_{gp}-T_2$ space.

The result yields from the above section was an application of optimal choices using the idea of $(KS_{gp})KS_{gp}-T_i$ ($i = 0,1,2$) on the content of these Kasaj topological structure. The idea of this application is based on personality characteristics of the applicants.

4 Conclusion

The class of $KS_{gp}(KS_{gsp})$ -open and $KS_{gp}(KS_{gsp})$ -closed sets has an important role to examine the separation axiom in Kasaj topological space. In this work, we studied new types of separation axioms namely, KS_{gp} - T_i , ($i=0,1,2$) spaces; KS_{gsp} - T_i , ($i=0,1,2$) spaces and the relation between spaces are discussed in new form. Several characterizations and the relation between properties of the above sets of separation axioms are discussed and proved. Furthermore, useful results are investigated by comparing $KS_{gp}(KS_{gsp})$ - T_0 spaces, $KS_{gp}(KS_{gsp})$ - T_1 , $KS_{gp}(KS_{gsp})$ - T_2 spaces in the context of these new concepts.

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